

FLEXURAL BEHAVIOR OF FOAM CORED SANDWICH STRUCTURES WITH THROUGH-THICKNESS REINFORCEMENTS

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Introduction

Vehicle crashworthiness and body weight are two important requirements in automotive applications. Composite sandwich structures are the preferred materials to be used in the body in white (BIW), as it must include areas of controlled deformation that have the aim of reducing the overall deceleration and protect the occupants during an impact event.

Sandwich structures are high stiffness and high strength materials which can provide superior energy absorption on performance over conventional metallic structures, with respect to weight. Therefore, both characterisation and modelling of these materials become crucial for improving and accelerating the design process (Fig.1).

In this study, sandwich panels with CFRP skins and a polymeric foam core (Fig.2) were considered and the effect of inserting CFRP through-thickness reinforcements on the panel flexural response was investigated.

Fig.2 Sandwich panel with foam core and CFRP skins and through-thickness reinforcement

Fig.1 Methodological approach

Experimental Methods

Three point bending tests were performed on sandwich panels with three different configurations (Fig.3):

- Configuration 1: No CFRP through-thickness reinforcements
- Configuration 2: One CFRP rib positioned underneath the loading roller
- Configuration 3: Two CFRP ribs

All the samples showed failure in both core and skins: foam shear cracks, foam crushing, skin-core debonding, delamination, matrix cracking and fiber breaking within the skins.

Fig.3 Experimental tests on sandwich panels with (a) Configuration 1 (b) Configuration 2 and (c) Configuration 3

Numerical Model

Material properties of the foam and skins were measured by mechanical testing (uniaxial tension, compression and shear tests) and were used as input for the finite element modelling (FEM) in Abaqus/Explicit.

The numerical models were validated by comparing the FEA results to the experimental results in terms of strain contours (Fig.4) and of load-displacement curves (Fig.5). The experimental strain maps were obtained with the digital image correlation (DIC) technique.

Fig.4 Comparison between DIC and FEA strain contours for (a) Configuration 1 (b) Configuration 2 and (c) Configuration 3

Fig.5 Comparison between experimental and FEA load-displacement curves for (a) Configuration 1 (b) Configuration 2 and (c) Configuration 3

Key Findings

- Core shear failure was the first failure mechanism occurring in all three configurations considered, followed by skin-core debonding and failure of the skins.
- Configuration 3 showed the best response in terms of loading bearing capability after failure (Fig.6) as the damage, and in particular the skin-core debonding, was confined within the region between the two CFRP ribs (Fig.7).
- In the FEM, both core and skin failure were accurately predicted with the use of appropriate failure criteria for the polymeric foam and the CFRP face sheets.
- Skin-core debonding was simulated as foam failure and captured by the foam failure criterion. Interface elements (cohesive elements) or crack modelling techniques (VCCT, XFEM) were no longer needed and the computational time for the simulation was reduced.

Fig.6 Comparison of the experimental load-displacement curves for the three specimen configurations

Fig.7 DIC σ (correlation coefficient) obtained during the testing of a specimen with Configuration 3